

From 5G to 6G: Empowering Vertical Industries with Next-Gen Technologies and Trial Facilities

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Abstract—In the fifth-generation (5G) era, there are opportunities for innovation in various vertical industries, including Transport and Logistics (T&L) and automotive, among others. For instance, the automotive sector can advance with edge computing nodes connected through network slices, providing more reliable teleoperation of vehicles, and enhancing vehicle-to-everything (V2X) use cases. However, widespread adoption of these technologies (e.g., edge computing, teleoperation of vehicles, V2X) has been limited, partly due to a lack of resources to test and explore among verticals to experience the potential improvements that 5G and Beyond (B5G) networks can offer to them. Thus, establishing B5G trial facilities is crucial. These facilities enable real-life B5G deployments across various verticals and serve as collaborative ecosystems where industries, telecom providers, and academia can co-create tailored services to meet specific operational needs.

As the sixth-generation (6G) era approaches, it is important to equip trial facilities with cutting-edge B5G technologies to support advanced vertical services. This article examines key 5G and B5G technologies for vertical industries, analyzing 40 major trial facilities to assess their capabilities. In addition, offering insights and recommendations to enhance trial facilities for testing and validating innovative vertical use cases in the 6G era.

Index Terms—5G, B5G, T&L, Trial facilities, Network slicing, Network functions, Sustainability.

I. INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

The enterprise market in the sixth-generation (6G) era for the vertical industry is expected to grow even stronger than fifth-generation (5G), which is estimated to reach \$2.9 trillion by 2026 [1]. Vertical industries refer to specific sectors of the economy that focus on a particular type of product, service, or market niche, characterized by specialized business needs, operational processes, and regulatory requirements. Examples of vertical industries include automotive, Transport & Logistics (T&L), e-health, manufacturing, smart cities, and energy. New 5G technologies are being designed and tested in various trial facilities to offer advanced connectivity capabilities for vertical industries and embed them tighter into the future 6G ecosystems. Among these Beyond 5G (B5G) technologies are intelligent network slicing, network exposure, and Edge Network Applications, as shown in Fig. 1 and further discussed in this article. In addition to these advancements, vertical industries should continue to explore even more basic functionalities such as Baseline 5G, which are also shown in Fig. 1 and will be further discussed in this article.

There are several challenges for vertical industries, such as automotive, T&L, and e-health, among others, to fully explore the untapped potential of B5G networks [1–4]:

Fig. 1: Overview of 6G Ecosystem.

- **Lack of Expertise Network-related knowledge Among Verticals:** This hinders verticals' ability to fully comprehend the potential benefits these networks could bring to their daily operations. Historically, this issue partially stems from the isolation of telecommunications standard organizations, such as the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) system, from the needs of vertical industries.
- **Limited Support for Real-World Testing Environments:** The lack of awareness about where and how verticals can efficiently test and validate their B5G vertical services in real-life B5G trial facilities, as usually, they need to invest in their own infrastructure to be able to test new capabilities, which is costly and time-consuming. Therefore, to validate the new upcoming B5G technologies, which are listed in Fig. 1 and will be further discussed in the article, large-scale trial facilities must replicate diverse, realistic environments that align with practical use cases, such as urban ecosystems or specific industrial applications.
- **Complexity of Integrating Advanced Network Technologies:** As 6G research focuses on sophisticated technologies like Artificial Intelligence (AI)-driven automation and intelligent network slicing, trial facilities must address the complexity of integrating these B5G technologies into existing infrastructure, ensuring seamless operation and applicability in real-world scenarios.
- **High Costs of Infrastructure Deployment and Maintenance:** Large-scale trials are essential for mimicking real-life networks, allowing experimenters (e.g., vertical industries) to first test technologies and capabilities before investing in their infrastructure. Additionally, cost-effective solutions such as infrastructure sharing and virtualization should be also tested in such trial environments, to help

industrial stakeholders decide on the optimal business model.

- **Low Energy Efficiency and limited Sustainability:** 6G trial facilities must address the rising demand for energy-efficient technologies to reduce operational costs and environmental impact, utilizing AI-driven optimizations for smarter energy management.
- **Poor Scalability and Management of Diverse Applications Across Verticals:** Meeting the diverse needs of vertical industries in 6G requires trial facilities to scale efficiently, leveraging advanced orchestration and programmable network capabilities to ensure optimal resource management.

Despite the emerging trends and the need for designing networks in a vertical-friendly manner, only a few works focus on vertical services in the B5G era. Nekovee et al. [5] outline a conceptual vision for a 6G-Enabled Internet of Verticals (6G-IoV), illustrating future scenarios of seamless interconnectivity across industries such as manufacturing, robotics, and energy, enabled by advancements like network slicing, edge computing, and deterministic networking. Complementing this, in [6], the same authors delve into key architectural and networking innovations, such as private networks and deterministic networking that underpin the transition from 5G to 6G, driving advancements in these verticals towards a 6G-IoV.

Schwentek et al. [7] provide a comprehensive 6G perspective from Mobile Network Operators (MNOs), manufacturers, and verticals, emphasizing the collaborative ecosystem required for integration. Penttinen et al. [8] detail 6G visions and requirements, highlighting strategic technologies such as network slicing for optimized resource allocation, enhanced integration of physical and digital worlds through digital twins, and support for emerging use cases like holographic communication and brain-machine interfaces. These strategic technologies aim to achieve superior connectivity, ultra-low latency, and advanced network programmability.

In-depth surveys such as Wang et al. [9] highlight the technical requirements for 6G, focusing on enabling technologies like terahertz (THz) communication, Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS), semantic communications, and energy-neutral devices, as well as advancements in testbeds for validating these technologies. While it provides valuable insights into technical advancements and testbed capabilities, it does not distinguish between Baseline 5G and B5G technologies nor explore their implications for vertical industries.

Our work addresses this gap by explicitly differentiating between Baseline 5G technologies (e.g., network slicing, edge computing) and advanced B5G technologies (e.g., network exposure, intelligent network slicing) as depicted in Fig. 1 and analyzing their benefits for various vertical industries. Furthermore, while the survey highlights testbeds at a high level, our work goes a step further by analyzing a broad set of large-scale trial facilities deployed across Europe. We analyze how these technologies specifically address the needs of various vertical industries and how European trial facilities are being used to test and validate these technologies for real-world use cases. This targeted focus allows us to propose actionable recommendations for evolving these facilities to support the seamless integration of vertical services.

Despite these research efforts from the works mentioned above, critical network technologies and frameworks like the NetWork Data Analytics Function (NWDAF), Network Slice Selection Function (NSSF)/Network Slice Management Func-

tion (NSMF), Network Exposure Function (NEF), and service Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) (e.g., Service Enabler Architecture Layer (SEAL) from 3GPP and CAMARA from Global System for Mobile Communications Association (GSMA)) remain underexplored, but are crucial for realizing the full potential of 6G. Moreover, these works mainly focus on functionalities without relying on current standardization efforts, making their adoption even more difficult. Our work goes a step further by analyzing a broad set of large-scale trial facilities specifically tailored to vertical trials deployed across Europe. We evaluate how these facilities are used for testing and validating key Baseline 5G and B5G technologies, as depicted in Fig. 1, for diverse real-world use cases, ranging from T&L to healthcare and manufacturing.

Therefore, in this article, we identify a subset of unique Baseline 5G and B5G technologies that can be considered essential building blocks to further enhance vertical services in the 6G era, as depicted in Fig. 1. Furthermore, to the best of our knowledge, our work uniquely investigates these technologies and analyzes their presence in 40 major vertical trial facilities, thereby providing insights on how current or newly created trial facilities can be upgraded to enable testing and validation of B5G vertical services. Our analysis focuses on the European landscape, analyzing a diverse set of trial sites deployed across the European Union (EU).

We selected these trial facilities because they originate from projects specifically focused on pioneering innovations with 5G and B5G technologies for vertical industries. These projects were chosen based on their alignment with key European strategic initiatives, such as 5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership (5G-PPP) and Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU), and their relevance to real-world industry needs. The selection process ensured technological diversity, geographical distribution across Europe, and the inclusion of facilities supporting large-scale trials and complex use cases. Although our analysis focuses on European facilities, the selected projects tackle challenges and use cases of global relevance, offering insights transferable to international contexts. This comprehensive view of Baseline and B5G technologies in existing trial sites, along with insights into their evolution, will help researchers identify network bottlenecks and guide industry trends.

To tackle the above-listed challenges, such as the lack of expertise network-related knowledge among verticals and the complexity of integrating advanced network technologies, this article provides the following contributions:

- Identification of critical Baseline 5G and B5G technologies for vertical services (contribution 1).
- Comprehensive analysis of 40 large-scale European 5G and B5G trial facilities tailored to vertical services (contribution 2).
- Evaluation of the adaptation of Baseline 5G and B5G technologies to application use cases in 40 large-scale European 5G and B5G trial facilities tailored to vertical services (contribution 3).
- Recommendations for future 6G trial facilities tailored to vertical services (contribution 4).

The remainder of this article is organized as follows: Section II presents an overview of Baseline 5G technologies, such as network slicing and edge computing, and their applications within vertical industries (contribution 1). Section III explores B5G technologies, including the integration of network exposure frameworks like Common API Framework (CAPIF)

TABLE I: List of abbreviations.

Description	Acronym
3rd Generation Partnership Project	3GPP
6G-Enabled Internet of Verticals	6G-IoV
Access and Mobility Management Function	AMF
Amazon Web Services	AWS
Application Programming Interface	API
Artificial Intelligence	AI
Beyond 5G	B5G
California Consumer Privacy Act	CCPA
Common API Framework	CAPIF
Downlink	DL
Edge Network-aware Application	EdgeApp
European Telecommunications Standards Institute	ETSI
Extended Reality	XR
Fifth-generation	5G
Global System for Mobile Communications Association	GSMA
Industrial Internet of Things	IIoT
Machine Learning	ML
Mobile Network Operator	MNO
Multi-access Edge Computing	MEC
NetWork Data Analytics Function	NWDAF
Network Exposure Function	NEF
Network Function	NF
Network Slice Management Function	NSMF
Network Slice Selection Function	NSSF
Open Gateway Initiative	OGI
Open Radio Access Network	O-RAN
Quality of Experience	QoE
Quality of Service	QoS
Radio Access Network	RAN
Return on Investment	ROI
Service Enabler Architecture Layer	SEAL
Service-Level Agreement	SLA
Session Management Function	SMF
Sixth-generation	6G
Small and Medium-sized Enterprise	SME
Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking	SNS JU
Standalone	SA
Time-Sensitive Networking	TSN
Transport and Logistics	T&L
Uplink	UL
United States of America	U.S.
User Equipment	UE
Vehicle-to-everything	V2X
Vertical Application Enabler	VAE
Virtual Reality	VR
Zero-touch Network & Service Management	ZSM

and SEAL from 3GPP and CAMARA from GSMA, and their impact on vertical services (contribution 1). Section IV provides a detailed analysis of the 40 European trial facilities and the use cases they host, showcasing real-world vertical services enabled by these facilities, where we map the identified Baseline and B5G technologies for each trial facility to highlights the challenges and innovations tested at these sites (contribution 2 and 3). Section V provides recommendations for future 6G trial facilities, focusing on sustainability, scalability, cost-efficiency, and their alignment with the needs of vertical industries (contribution 4). Table I provides a comprehensive list of all abbreviations used throughout this article.

II. BASELINE 5G

In this section, we focus on the subset of Baseline 5G capabilities that vertical industries are currently benefiting from in various trial facilities, as shown in Fig. 2, which illustrates the transition from Baseline 5G to B5G technologies. We refer to Baseline 5G as the initial set of standards that provide the essential functionality to make 5G operational, corresponding to 3GPP Release 15 up to 3GPP Release 16. The Baseline 5G specifies the initial technologies and capabilities of 5G networks, such as network slicing and edge computing.

The 5G Core (Fig. 2) is the central component of any 5G network architecture, designed to manage network functions, such as NEF, Session Management Function (SMF), and Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF) to ensure seamless connectivity and service delivery. It incorporates advanced technologies such as network slicing, virtualization, and edge computing to enable high-speed, low-latency communication. The 5G Core, which makes 5G Standalone (SA), is completely virtualized and softwarized, which improves the management of Core functions and ultimately impacts the Quality of Service (QoS) perceived by end users, such as, vertical industries.

Within the 5G and B5G ecosystem, edge computing represents computing, memory, and storage facilities located in the network (Fig. 2). In Baseline 5G, edge computing is important for verticals as it allows them to deploy their services in their proximity, benefiting from reduced latencies compared to cloud environments. For example, data from Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) sensors (e.g., smart meters, industrial equipment) can be processed locally at the edge to improve response times and reduce bandwidth usage.

The concept of network slicing was first introduced by the 3GPP in Release 16. Network slicing enables the creation of multiple virtualized and logically isolated networks on a shared physical infrastructure, each tailored to specific requirements such as latency, bandwidth, and reliability (Fig. 2) [1]. According to Afolabi et al. [10] and their comprehensive survey regarding the current maturity level of network slicing in Baseline 5G, verticals can incorporate the development of vertical services leveraging the slicing paradigm. At the same time, MNOs can create partnerships to accelerate network slice service roll-outs and could focus on creating customized slice services tailored to vertical services [10].

III. BEYOND 5G

Currently, 3GPP is defining 5G-Advanced starting from Release 18, which is expected to introduce new key features and technologies, paving the way toward the 6G era. 5G-Advanced is anticipated to include major enhancements in areas such as AI, Extended Reality (XR)/Virtual reality (VR), Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN), joint communications and sensing, mmWave, PHY layer advancements, and more.

However, we provide a comprehensive overview of a subset of those 5G-Advanced technologies (Fig. 2), focusing on benefits for vertical industries, and we refer to them as B5G. As we progress towards the 6G era, the exploration and development of advanced technologies within the 5G context are crucial for realizing B5G networks vision of enabling highly intelligent edge network services to support a broader array of use cases.

A. Specific 3GPP initiatives focused on vertical services

The main objective of the 3GPP Application Enablement & Critical Communication Applications working group (SA WG 6) is to incentivize vertical industries to leverage the

Fig. 2: Empowering Vertical Industries with next-gen technologies and facilities, from Baseline 5G towards B5G technologies (example vertical services teleoperation and autonomous driving).

3GPP technology in their services by abstracting the network complexity. Therefore, this working group is focused on incorporating verticals in the complex B5G ecosystem through key enabling service frameworks, which we further discuss in this section. The goal of the service frameworks is to simplify the implementation and deployment of vertical services at a large scale capable of dynamically re-programming the underlying B5G network [11].

1) **Common API Framework (CAPIF)**: The role of CAPIF (Fig. 2) is to standardize APIs across 3GPP network functions starting from Release 16 and facilitate the integration of vertical applications into 5G and B5G systems. These efforts underline the growing importance and impact of CAPIF in shaping the future of telecommunications networks.

The Horizon ICT 41 project named "Experimentation and Validation Openness for Longterm evolution of Vertical industries in 5G era and beyond" or EVOLVED-5G leverages CAPIF for vertical service to promote the openness and programmability of 5G and B5G networks to vertical industries. In recent work from the same project, Sanchez et al. [12] provide this framework as a flexible deployable microservice for vertical industries, boosting the ease of use by verticals. However, as with all APIs, security is of high importance, especially

for vertical services, as they contain sensitive information. Therefore, Stylianou et al. [13] propose to incorporate the Open ID Connect (OIDC)/OAuth2.0 authentication and authorization protocol in the CAPIF Framework standard to enhance the security characteristics.

2) **Service Enabler Architecture Layer (SEAL)**: The objective of SEAL (3GPP Release 16.) (Fig. 2) is to standardize a service architecture for vertical applications in the 5G and B5G ecosystem. SEAL provides a functional architecture and information flows that enable the exposure of network capabilities and services to third-party applications, such as vertical applications. It serves as an intermediary layer between the network functions and the applications, thereby simplifying the process of leveraging network capabilities for diverse use cases. The SEAL framework is designed to be flexible and adaptable, supporting a wide range of verticals and use cases. It provides a standardized CAPIF API specification, which is outlined in TS 29.5492.

Fragkos et al. [11] investigated how the 5G and B5G architectures will support Vertical Application Enabler (VAE) in 3GPP networks from Release 17 onwards, and they acknowledge that SEAL is a valid framework to support VAEs e.g., for vehicle-to-everything (V2X) use cases.

3) **Application Architecture for Edge Apps (EDGEAPP):** Another important 3GPP service framework, outlined in TS 23.558, is the EDGEAPP framework (Fig. 2). This framework provides an edge-enabling layer and application architecture to support Edge Applications, similar to how European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) defines ETSI Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC), and the GSMA defines the GSMA-Operating Platform (OP), which are two other leading-edge standard architectures.

The objective of the EDGEAPP framework is to enable edge computing within the 3GPP framework to meet the specific latency, reliability, and bandwidth requirements of various verticals. The EDGEAPP framework facilitates the hosting of applications on the edge, ensuring their seamless integration with the 3GPP network. This includes the exposure of northbound CAPIF APIs towards Edge Applications, integration with the 3GPP network, and the facilitation of communication between application clients running on User Equipment (UE) and Edge Application Servers deployed on the Edge of the network. These capabilities encompass service provisioning, rich application discovery, and service continuity, thereby enhancing the overall functionality and efficiency of edge computing solutions.

However, as noted by Pham et al. [14], several challenges persist, necessitating a thorough examination to establish an edge ecosystem that benefits all stakeholders in the network, including IoT users, service/infrastructure providers, and MNOs. That is why in our prior work [1], we present the EdgeApp framework which extends beyond the ETSI MEC and the existing 3GPP service frameworks (SEAL, CAPIF, and EDGEAPP) as these frameworks do not take into account the specific requirements (network, service, and hardware) from verticals when deploying them into the 5G and B5G network.

4) **NetWork Data Analytics Function (NWDAF):** This function is standardized by 3GPP [15], as a specialized network function focused on network data analytics, which collects, processes, and analyzes vast amounts of network data in real-time (e.g., data from UEs, Network Functions (NFs) within the 5G Core, Edge, and Cloud networks). The main objective of this function is to provide actionable insights and intelligence to various network functions and management systems. By employing advanced analytics techniques such as Machine Learning (ML) and AI, NWDAF can identify patterns, predict network behavior, detect anomalies, and recommend optimizations.

Currently, there is no open-source implementation of this function [15], but its importance for 6G and AI-native networks creates a strong incentive for its development. It would create more opportunities for stakeholders through iterative testing and experimentation. For example, researchers and industry can identify opportunities for optimization, validate algorithms, and explore innovative vertical applications.

5) **Network Slice Management Function (NSMF)/Network Slice Selection Function (NSSF):** These functions are responsible for managing and orchestrating network slices. They work in tandem to ensure efficient utilization of network resources and optimal performance (Fig. 2).

The NSMF is responsible for the lifecycle management of network slices, i.e., the creation, configuration, and decommissioning of network slices. This function also handles resource allocation, dynamic adaptation of network slice configurations, inter-slice coordination, and policy-based slice management. The NSSF, on the other hand, is responsible for selecting the most appropriate network slice for a given service request.

It makes selection and allocation decisions accounting for latency, throughput, reliability, security, and specific service characteristics. It also enforces policy rules defined by the network operator or service provider. The availability of the NSMF/NSSF within trial facilities fosters collaboration and knowledge sharing between researchers and industry, accelerating the development and adoption of next-generation intelligent network-slicing solutions.

B. Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN)

The goal O-RAN is to promote openness and vendor-neutrality in Radio Access Network (RAN) hardware and software (Fig. 2). Driven by operators, vendors, standard organizations, and academia, O-RAN challenges the traditionally proprietary and monolithic RAN landscape, where hardware and software were tightly coupled to specific vendors [16]. By enabling interoperability and modularity, O-RAN allows operators to mix and match components from different vendors, fostering competition and driving innovation for enhanced network services.

Having O-RAN functionality within 5G testbeds is important for the following reasons: i) Interoperability Testing across different vendors, ii) Innovation and Experimentation: enabling researchers, developers, and operators to experiment with O-RAN architectures, explore new use cases, and develop innovative solutions and, iii) Education and Training: Open testbeds provide educational opportunities for students, researchers, and industry professionals, to gain hands-on experience with O-RAN technologies.

C. Network Exposure Capabilities

The B5G networks will need increased network exposure which provides controlled, standardized access to various network functionalities and resources. For example, standardized APIs provide access to network slicing, location services, dynamic bandwidth Uplink (UL)/Downlink (DL) allocation, data analytics, and monitoring (Fig. 2). This allows vertical applications and their services to interact directly with the underlying network to impact QoS and Quality of Experience (QoE).

To further enhance automation and adaptability in these networks, Intent-based network (IBN) is emerging as a key enabler for such intelligent resource orchestration [17]. IBN allows vertical service providers to define high-level business intents, which are then translated into real-time network configurations through AI-driven automation. By leveraging IBN in network exposure, networks can dynamically adjust performance parameters (e.g., required uplink throughput) based on vertical needs, ensuring optimized service delivery across diverse industries.

An important initiative for network exposure capabilities is facilitated by the GSMA and the Linux Foundation. The Open Gateway Initiative (OGI) initiated by GSMA, plays a pivotal role in standardizing network exposure APIs, promoting interoperability between MNOs and third-party developers. These APIs are defined, developed, and published within CAMARA, an open-source project aimed at providing developers with access to enhanced network capabilities. The CAMARA APIs are compatible with 3GPP CAPIF framework [18], and some implementations are provided by Nokia (Network-as-Code) [19] and Ericsson (Vonage) [20].

D. Native AI Networks

The B5G networks are envisioned to be AI native, and 6G will employ AI-driven automation and optimization across all layers of the network, from core to edge [21]. This integration will enable real-time data analysis, predictive maintenance, dynamic resource allocation, and adaptive security measures, thereby significantly improving the networks responsiveness and reliability. This requires advanced orchestration mechanisms, to make network management highly automated, leveraging technologies such as Zero-touch Network & Service Management (ZSM) and dynamic network slicing.

Both ZSM and dynamic slicing result in enhanced resource allocation efficiency and improved QoS/QoE. However, as highlighted by Coronado et al. [22] in their thorough survey of ZSM, one of the significant research challenges in ZSM paradigm is the availability of high-quality and representative datasets. This underscores the importance of equipping B5G vertical trial facilities with state-of-the-art monitoring solutions to support ZSM, thereby enabling the generation of more realistic datasets, as already specified within the context of verticals.

Another important aspect is energy efficiency, as B5G networks need to minimize environmental impact and reduce energy costs [21]. The European research project BeGREEN states that B5G networks controlled by AI could achieve energy savings exceeding 50% compared to current 5G, with e.g., demand-based switch on/off of radio receivers. However, it is important that these network energy savings are applied across all the network segments (RAN, Core, Edge).

IV. B5G TRIAL FACILITIES FOR VERTICAL SERVICES

In this section, we analyze 40 important 5G and B5G trial facilities from three key programs: i) H2020 **ICT-41**, which brings 5G innovations for verticals with third-party services and smart connectivity, ii) SNS JU Phase 1 **Stream C**, focused on experimental infrastructures for smart services, and iii) SNS JU Phase 1 **Stream D**, tailored to large-scale trials for vertical industries. This article focuses on the initial Phase of SNS JU, as subsequent Phases (2 and 3) are currently insufficiently documented. By consolidating insights from Phase 1, this article also aims to serve as a valuable resource for ongoing and future projects, offering strategic guidance in the design and validation of forthcoming trial facilities.

We identify Baseline 5G and B5G technologies in these trial facilities because they need to be equipped with state-of-the-art technologies for implementing and verifying new vertical innovations in real-world scenarios. Fig. 3 provides an overview of all the large-scale trial facilities discussed in this article, along with their corresponding B5G application use cases.

A. Real-world applications tested and demonstrated in trial facilities across the project categories

All the trial facilities highlighted in this article have enabled a wide range of real-world applications and vertical services across Europe. Tables IV and V highlight the specific B5G technologies (Table III) leveraged by each application use case, such as network exposure and advanced network slicing solutions. While the Baseline 5G technologies are not included in these tables, all applications leverage the available Baseline 5G technologies provided by the specific testbed (Table II).

The trial facilities from **ICT-41** program are generally focused on:

Fig. 3: Overview of implementation of B5G applications on the European landscape.

- **Public Protection and Disaster Relief (PPDR):** Examples include drone-assisted fire detection, medical diagnosis tools, and robot-based ecosystem assessment. These applications demonstrate how 5G facilitates rapid communication and real-time information sharing among first responders.
- **Automotive & T&L Applications:** Use cases such as autonomous vehicles, teleoperation of vehicles and vessels, situational awareness for cross-border tunnels, and remote driving illustrate 5G's role in advancing automotive safety and efficiency.
- **Industry 4.0:** Highlights applications like predictive maintenance, Augmented reality (AR)-based remote support and industrial process anomaly detection, showing 5G's influence on smart manufacturing and critical infrastructure monitoring.

Compared to the ICT-41 program the **Stream C** program incentivizes more extensive external participants, such as Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs), researchers, and industry players, to innovate and extend the testbed capabilities through funded open calls. Through the open calls, the experimental infrastructure is enhanced. At the same time, it enables real-world trials of emerging technologies to let vertical industries explore how B5G technologies can improve their day-to-day operations.

- **XR and Metaverse:** Focus on immersive applications, such as real-time holographic communication and digital twin

TABLE II: Trial facilities with Baseline 5G capabilities.

Projects	Trial Facilities		Baseline 5G		
	Name	Type of 5G Core	Core Release	Edge Computing	Network Slicing
5GASP [23,24]	ITAv – Aveiro Portugal	Huawei commercial Core	Rel. 16	Edge	Yes
	UoP – Patras5G Greece	Open5GCore	Rel. 16	Edge	Yes
	5GUKTest, UK	Open5GS	Rel. 16	Edge	Yes
	Orange Romania (ORO) Bucharest	Nokia (CMU), Ericsson; Mosaic5G	Rel. 16	MEC	Yes
	Gaia-5G - Murcia	Amarisoft, Opensource5G Cores	Rel. 15	MEC	No
	ININ Ljubljana	Not specified	Rel. 15	Edge	No
5G-EPICENTRE [25]	5GNESIS – UMA Malaga, Spain	Nokia, Private network	Rel. 16	Edge	No
	5G-VINNI – Aveiro, Portugal	Open5GCore, OpenNESS	Rel. 16	Edge	No
	5G-Berlin, Germany	Not specified	Rel. 16	Edge	No
	CTC Barcelona, Spain	Amarisoft, Open5Gs	Rel. 16	Edge, Cloud	Yes
5G-IANA [26]	Ulm Nokia, Germany	Nokia, Private network	Rel. 16	Edge	Yes
	ININ, Ljubljana Slovenia	Not specified	Rel. 16	Edge	No
5G-INDUCE [27]	5Tonic – Valencia, Spain	Ericsson	Rel. 16	Edge, MEC	Yes
	OTE - Lavrio-Athens, Greece	Athonet packet Core	Rel. 16	Edge, MEC	No
	Genoa – Biandronno, Italy	Not specified	Rel. 15	Edge, MEC	No
EVOLVED-5G [28,29]	5Glink, Athens, Greece	OpenDaylight	Rel. 16	Edge	Yes
	UMA campus, Malaga, Spain	Not specified	Rel. 16	Edge	Yes
VITAL-5G [30,31]	IMEC, Telenet – Antwerp	Nokia	Rel. 16	Edge, MEC	Yes
	Orange Romania (ORO) – Bucharest	Nokia (CMU), Ericsson, Mosaic5G	Rel. 16	Edge, MEC	Yes
	OTE, Athens, Greece	Atonet, Griffone	Rel. 16	Edge, MEC	Yes
SNS-JU Stream C projects					
6G-SANDBOX [32,33]	OTE Academy, NCSR Demokritos campus Athens, Greece	AMARISOFT, Open5GS, Ericsson	Rel. 16	MEC	Yes
	FOKUS, Berlin, Germany	AMARISOFT	Rel. 16	Edge	No
	University of Malaga Spain	Ploaris 5GC Unicorn	Rel. 16	Edge, MEC	Yes
	CWC research unit at Oulu	OpenEPC	Rel. 16	No	No
6G-BRICKS [34,35]	KUL, Leuven, Belgium	Not specified	Rel. 16	Deep Edge	No
	Sophia Tech Open5GLab, France	Patria 3GPP 5GC	Rel. 16	MEC	Yes
6G-XR [36,37]	5Gtonic, Madrid, Spain	Ericsson	Rel. 17	Edge, MEC	Yes
	5G-Barcelona	Open5GS, Free5GC	Rel. 17	Edge	No
	5GTN VTT Technical Research centre, Finland	Open5GS	Rel. 17	Edge MEC	Yes
	5G Test Network at University of Oulu, Finland	Open5GS	Rel. 17	Edge MEC	Yes
SNS-JU Stream D projects					
TARGET-X [38,39]	5G-ICE 5G Industry Campus Europe	Ericsson (indoor) Private network	Rel. 15	Edge	No
	Idiada Automotive (IDAID), Spain	Open5GS	Rel. 15	Edge	No
TrialsNet [40,41]	Orange Romania, IMEC Antwerp	Nokia , Ericsson	Rel. 16	Edge, MEC	Yes
	Turin site, Italy	Ericsson , public network	Rel. 16	MEC	Yes
	5Tonic Madrid, Spain	Ericsson	Rel. 17	Edge, MEC	Yes
	Greece, site	Not specified	Rel. 16	Edge,MEC,Cloud	Yes
FIDAL [42–44]	Patras5G/PNET, Greece	Open5GS, Amarisoft , Free5GC	Rel. 18	Edge	Yes
	UMA VICTORIA – Malaga Spain	Polaris, Networks, Open5GS	Rel. 16	Edge	Yes
	Telnor LST Facility Norway	A multi vendor solution collaboratively provided by Oracle, ENEA and CasaSystem	Rel. 16	Edge Cloud	Yes
IMAGINE-BG5 [45,46]	EURECOM SophiaTech Open5GLab France	Open5GS	Rel. 16	Edge, Cloud	Yes
	Telnor, Nokia-Finland, Norway	Nokia	Rel. 17	MEC	Yes
	Altice Labs, Portugal	Open5GS4,Huawei 5G Core,Open5GCore	Rel. 17	MEC	Yes
	Telefonica, Nokia-Spain, Spain	Open5GS, Cumucore, Amarisoft	Rel. 16	Edg, Cloud	Yes

TABLE III: Trial facilities with B5G capabilities.

Projects	Trial Facilities		Beyond 5G						
	Name	CAPIF/SEAL/EDGEAPP	O-RAN	NWDAF	NSSF/ NSMF	Network Exposure Capabilities	Advanced Slicing	ZSM	Network Applications EdgeApps
ICT-41	ITAv – Aveiro Portugal	No	No	No	NSSF	No	No	No	Yes
	UoP – Patras5G Greece	No	No	No	No	NEF Emulator	Yes	No	Yes
	5GUKTest, UK	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
	Orange Romania (ORO) Bucharest	No	Yes	No	NSSF	No	No	No	Yes
	Gaia-5G - Murcia	No	No	No	NSSF	NEF Emulator	Yes	No	Yes
	ININ Ljubljana	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
5G-EPICENTRE	5GNESIS – UMA Malaga, Spain	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
	5G-VINNI – Aveiro, Portugal	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
	5G-Berlin, Germany	No	No	No	No	No	Beam forming	No	Yes
5G-IANA	CTTC Barcelona, Spain	Yes	No	No	NSSF	No	No	No	Yes
	Ulm Nokia, Germany	No	No	No	NSSF	No	No	No	Yes
	ININ, Ljubljana Slovenia	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
5G-INDUCE	5Tonic – Valencia, Spain	No	No	No	NSSF	No	No	No	Yes
	OTE - Lavrio-Athens, Greece	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
	Genoa – Biandronno, Italy	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
EVOLVED -5G	5Glink, Athens, Greece	CAPIF	No	No	NSSF	NEF Simulator	No	No	Yes
	UMA campus, Malaga, Spain	CAPIF	No	Yes	NSSF	NEF Simulator	No	No	Yes
VITAL-5G	IMEC, Telenor – Antwerp	No	No	No	NSSF	NEF with CAMARA	No	No	Yes
	Orange Romania (ORO) – Bucharest	No	No	No	NSSF	No	No	No	Yes
	OTE, Athens, Greece	No	No	No	NSSF	No	No	No	Yes
SNS-JU Stream C projects									
6G- SANDBOX	OTE Academy, NCSR Demokritos campus Athens, Greece	CAPIF	No	Yes	NSSF	-NEF Emulator -Ericsson NEF	KATANA slice solution	No	Yes
	FOKUS, Berlin, Germany	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
	University of Malaga Spain	No	Yes	No	NSSF	No	No	No	Yes
	CWC research unit at Oulu	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
6G-BRICKS	KUL, Leuven, Belgium	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No
	Sophia Tech Open5GLab, France	No	Yes	Yes	NSSF	No	No	No	Yes
6G-XR	5Gtonic, Madrid, Spain	CAPIF	No	No	NSSF	No	No	No	Yes
	5G-Barcelona	No	Yes	No	NSSF	No	No	No	Yes
	5GTN VTT Technical Research centre, Finland	No	Yes	No	NSSF	No	No	No	Yes
	5G Test Network at University of Oulu, Finland	No	Yes	No	NSSF	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
SNS-JU Stream D projects									
TARGET-X	5G-ICE 5G Industry Campus Europe	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
	Idiada Automotive (IDAID), Spain	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
TrialsNet	Orange Romania, IMEC Antwerp	CAPIF/SEAL	Yes	No	NSSF	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Turin site, Italy	No	No	No	NSSF	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
	5Tonic Madrid, Spain	CAPIF	No	NO	NSSF	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Greece, site	CAPIF	No	Yes	NSSF	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
FIDAL	Patras5G/PNET, Greece	CAPIF	Yes	Yes	NSSF	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
	UMA VICTORIA – Malaga Spain	No	Yes	No	NSSF	No	No	Yes	Yes
	Telnor LST Facility Norway	CAPIF	No	No	NSSF	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
IMAGINE- BG5	EURECOM SophiaTech Open5GLab France	CAPIF	Yes	No	NSSF NSMF	CAMARA NaC	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Telnor, Nokia-Finland, Norway	CAPIF	Yes	No	NSSF	CAMARA NaC	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Altice Labs, Portugal	CAPIF	No	Yes	NSSF	CAMAEA NaC	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Telefonica, Nokia-Spain, Spain	CAPIF	No	No	NSSF NSMF	CAMARA NaC	Yes	Yes	Yes

simulations for industrial environments. These use cases show how 6G will enable low-latency, high-reliability experiences. Open calls through this stream focus on expanding XR capabilities and validating Metaverse use cases, inviting proposals to enhance infrastructure and trial new applications in remote collaboration and industrial simulation.

- *Collaborative Robotics (Cobots) and Automation:* Examples include XR-based training environments and real-time collaborative robots for logistics. These applications illustrate 5G’s potential for streamlining human-robot collaboration and optimizing industrial workflows. Open calls

encourage the integration of new 6G functionalities for industrial automation, such as AI-driven network management and autonomous robotics, fostering innovation in Industry 4.0.

- *Data-Intensive Industrial Applications:* Stream C projects also focus on supporting data-heavy applications, such as real-time analytics for energy management, industrial Internet of Things (IoT), and digital twins. These applications demonstrate 6G’s potential for handling high-volume data processing. Open calls focus on expanding testbed capabilities for handling massive data flows, enabling verticals to trial advanced 6G applications like energy-

efficient networks, intelligent network operations, and ambient IoT.

Similar to the Stream C program, but then tailored to large-scale trials, the **Stream D** offers vertical industries open calls to facilitate collaborative testing and innovation in several key areas:

- **Cross-Industry Trials and Prototyping:** Stream D projects support applications across sectors such as automotive, energy, manufacturing, construction, and robotics. These trials explore use cases like predictive maintenance, digital twins, and energy-efficient solutions to showcase 5G and 6G's cross-industry impact. Open calls in this category invite third parties to prototype new devices and solutions or to enhance performance in areas like manufacturing, automotive, and energy.
- **Urban Ecosystem and Societal Applications:** Focus areas include infrastructure, transportation, security, eHealth, and culture. Applications like telemedicine, emergency services, and smart tourism illustrate how 5G and 6G can enhance urban environments, improve safety, and enrich cultural experiences. Open calls in this stream encourage stakeholders to experiment with new use cases or field trials on existing infrastructures. Proposals include integrating new software, devices, and services, as well as adding experimental setups across urban domains, enabling real-world validation of innovative solutions in diverse urban contexts.

B. Procedures for Vertical Companies to Engage with Trial Facilities via Open Calls

Vertical companies interested in leveraging trial facilities for their development can benefit from the open calls associated with SNS JU projects like those in Stream D. Open calls are designed to promote third-party involvement, enabling verticals to propose new use cases, validate technologies, or extend existing infrastructure capabilities. The general procedure for participation typically involves the following steps:

- 1) **Announcement and Eligibility:** Open calls are publicly announced by project consortia, often targeting SMEs, startups, and industry players with innovative vertical solutions. Eligibility criteria usually include alignment with the project's technological focus, geographical scope (e.g., EU-based entities), and the capacity to contribute to the project's goals.
- 2) **Proposal Submission:** Interested verticals submit a proposal outlining their intended use case, technical approach, and the expected benefits of leveraging the trial facility. Proposals must demonstrate how the use case aligns with the trial site's capabilities and addresses relevant industry challenges.
- 3) **Evaluation Process:** Submitted proposals undergo an evaluation based on predefined criteria such as technical innovation, relevance to vertical industry needs, scalability, and sustainability. Proposals showcasing high potential for cross-sector impact or societal benefits are often prioritized.
- 4) **Onboarding and Integration:** Selected verticals are onboarded to the trial facility. This phase may include satisfying specific technical requirements such as network compatibility (e.g., alignment with Baseline 5G or B5G technologies), compliance with security standards, and integration of APIs like CAPIF or SEAL for seamless network interaction.

- 5) **Testing and Validation:** The vertical solutions are tested within the trial facility, with the level of involvement varying from minimal configuration to deep technical collaboration, depending on the complexity of the use case. Support from the trial facility consortium is typically provided to ensure successful integration.
- 6) **Outcome Assessment and Dissemination:** Results from the trials are assessed in terms of performance metrics, scalability, and real-world applicability. Successful outcomes may lead to further collaborations, funding opportunities, or commercial deployments.

This general framework ensures that vertical companies can efficiently engage with trial facilities, fostering innovation and accelerating the adoption of 5G and B5G technologies across diverse sectors.

C. Trial facilities with Baseline 5G capabilities

When examining the Baseline 5G capabilities depicted in Table II, focusing on trial facilities from **ICT-41** program, we observe that all of them have edge computing capabilities. Additionally, 55% of the trial sites support basic network slicing, with 85% of the trial sites being equipped with 5G Core (Release 16). Furthermore, 45% are vendor-based 5G Cores, and 30% utilize open-source Cores (e.g., Open5Gs). The alignment of trial facilities with commercial 5G deployments in Europe (also Release 16-based) is important as it creates a realistic environment for vertical industries to test their services before investing in telco infrastructure. The remaining 35% open-source 5G Cores are valuable for testing modifications on the 5G Core, which can be further to telco networks, and eventually offered to vertical industries.

When reviewing the Baseline 5G capabilities of **Stream C** program (Table II), we observe that 60% of the 5G Cores are open-source, and 30% are vendor-based. In total, 40% of them are based on 3GPP Release 17. The majority being open-source is explainable, as these trial facilities are specifically tailored to enable vertical service providers and MNOs to create new services through experimental infrastructure, which mostly extends the current capabilities of vendor-based 5G Core deployments. Therefore, these trial facilities are especially relevant for smaller vertical service providers (e.g., SMEs, startups, etc.), as open-source 5G Cores enable them, and MNOs, to innovate and experiment without the high costs associated with proprietary solutions.

In the case of **Stream D** (Table II), we see that they are largely consistent with other initiatives. Here, the majority of the 5G Cores are vendor-based 59%, with 38.5% open-source.

D. Trial facilities with B5G capabilities

Now moving to B5G capabilities (Table III), we can see that all **ICT 41** trial facilities support the creation and deployment of Network Applications/Edge Network-aware Applications (EdgeApps). However, only 2 out of 40 support NWDAF and network exposure capabilities. Yet, it is important to highlight that some of these projects e.g., VITAL-5G, made custom platform components and tested network plugins that send similar network data analytics, mimicking NWDAF [1]. Concerning network exposure, once the vertical service is fully aware of the network conditions, it can dynamically reprogram the underlying B5G network. For example, it can boost UL/DL capacity to ensure the service remains within optimal network conditions and does not violate Service-Level Agreements (SLAs).

TABLE IV: B5G Network Applications in the ICT-41 Trial Facilities.

Trial facility	5G-Applications	B5G Feature
ITAv – Aveiro Portugal 5GASP	Privacy Analyzer (vertical agnostic) 5G Isolated Operations (PPDR)	NSSF Network Application
UoP – Patras5G Greece 5GASP	Fire Detection and Ground Assistance using Drones (FIDGAD) Privacy Analyzer (vertical agnostic)	NEF Emulator Advanced slicing Network Application
5GUKTest, UK, 5GASP	Efficient MEC handover (vertical agnostic)	O-RAN; Network Application
Orange Romania (ORO) Bucharest 5GASP	Vehicle Route Optimize (vertical agnostic) 5G Isolated Operations (PPDR)	NSSF Network Application
Gaia-5G - Murcia, Spain 5GASP	Automotive vertical: Virtual Onboard Unit (vOBU); Cooperative ITS Station; Virtual RoadSide Unit; Vehicle-to-cloud Real-Time Communication; Remote Human Driving	NEF Emulator Advanced slicing Network Application
ININ Ljubljana, Slovenia 5GASP	5G Isolated Operations (PPDR)	Network Application
5GNESIS – UMA Malaga, Spain 5G-EPICENTRE	5G PPDR for QoS & Slicing scenarios: Multimedia MC Communication and Collaboration Platform Slicing and QoS management in high-traffic conditions IoT for improving first responders; situational awareness and safety Auto-scaling video routers in 5G Edge AR and AI wearable electronics	Network Application
5G-VINNI – Atlice Labs veiro, Portugal 5G-EPICENTRE	5G PPDR for Video & Throughput 5G scenarios: IoT for improving first responders Auto-scaling video routers in 5G Edge	O-RAN Network Application
5G-Berlin, Germany 5G-EPICENTRE	5G PPDR for drone management scenarios: Ultra-reliable drone navigation and remote control Fast situational awareness and near real-time disaster mapping AR and AI wearable electronics for PPDR	Beam forming Network Application
CTTC Barcelona Spain5G-EPICENTRE	5G PPDR for Instantiation & Latency scenario: Multimedia MC Communication and Collaboration AR-assisted emergency surgical care	NSSF Network Application
Ulm Nokia, Germany 5G-IANA	Network Applications: Real-Time Stream Services, Object Detection Stream and Dataelivery; AGV Data Processing; Communication and Control; Remote driving; MCAD Edge Node; MCAD Rover Node; AI Enhanced Video Stream Delivery; Video-enabled VR Client;Active Network Monitoring Module; Virtual Bus Tour; AR streaming application; Real-time Hazardous driving event detection; Aggregated Hazardous driving event detection; Real-time vehicle trajectory; prediction, Hazardous driving event notification; Predictive QoS; Obtain Training Data; DML Training, Video stream delivery, Environmental/IoT monitoring; Simulator of ETSI Cooperative	NSSF Network Application
ININ, Ljubljana Slovenia 5G-IANA	Processes, L7-aware Whitebox Switch with Dynamic SFC & TSN Support SIEM (Security information and event management) system; IQBT: Blockchain Data Brokerage Engine; AI-driven Humanoid robot: AI-driven logistics robotic fleets; Smart irrigation system	Network Application
5Tonic - Valencia Spain, 5G-INDUCE	Autonomous indoor fleet management; Smart operation based on human gesture recognition;VR Immersion and AGV Control	NSSF; Network Application
OTE - Athens, Greece, 5G-INDUCE	Inspection and Surveillance of critical infrastructures; AR-based remote maintenance; Smart logistics; Drone base performance monitoring	Network Application
Genoa – Biandronno Italy, 5G-INDUCE	ML-Supported Edge Analytics for Predictive Maintenance; R-based remote maintenance; Drone base performance monitoring	Network Application
5Glink, AthensGreece EVOLVED-5G	Mixed Reality (MR) assisted manufacturing; Intent-driven Chatbots for precise maintenance; Haptic-driven console for industrial surface repairing (hot bonding); IoT/M2M-based remote monitoring platform,	CAPIF; NSSF NEF Simulator Network Application
UMA campus, Malaga Spain, EVOLVED-5G	AI-based video analyzer for industrial & robotics safety ML-driven anomaly detection system for Industrial	CAPIF; NSSF; NEF Simulator Network Application
IMEC, Telenet Antwerp VITAL-5G	T&L Maritime port Network Applications: Navigation Speed Optimizer; Assisted vessel navigation; Real-time digital twin; Onboard data Collection & interfacing for vessels; Monitoring dashboard	NSSF NEF with CAMARA Network Application
ORO - Bucharest VITAL-5G	T&L River port Network Applications: Distributed Sensor Data Ingestion; Fusion & Automation; Predictive Maintenance; Data Stream Organization; Network Data Collection; Technical Data visualization; Onboard Data Collection & Interfacing for NAVROM vessels	NSSF Network Application
OTE, Athens, Greece VITAL-5G	T&L Warehouse Network Applications: Distributed Sensor Data Ingestion; Fusion &Automation; Human-robot Collaboration; AI/ML Automated Fault Detection and Predictive Maintenance	NSSF Network Application

TABLE V: B5G Applications in the SNS JU Phase 1 stream C and D Trial Facilities.

Trial facility	B5G Applications	B5G Feature
OTE Academy NCSR Demokritos campus Athens, Greece 6G-SANDBOX	Open calls, to create new infrastructure and functionalities for the European experimentation: ONEmNEF – OneSource’s Microservice-based Network Exposure Function; analyticS and localization (NWDAF, Location Management Function (LMF)); ASTRAL – O-RAN research prototype for the 6G-SANDBOX platform; Expanding the 6G-Sandbox testbed With Content Distribution Networks for Quality of Experience; Augmenting 6G-SANDBOX with Terahertz communication capabilities; Experimentation: Remote mEdical Support and Communication Utility in Emergency; scenarios (RESCUE); NDWAF – StreamAnalyzer (only in Athens testbed); REACT-6G – RAN Intelligent Automation and Control via xApps Towards 6G; PowerStorm – Energy-Aware Streaming Analytics Job Scheduling for 5G/6G Deployments	CAPIF; NWDAF; NSSF; NEF Emulator + Ericsson solution KATANA slicing Network Application
FOKUS, Berlin, Germany 6G-SANDBOX	Open calls to create new infrastructure and functionalities for the European experimentation Same B5G applications as described above.	O-RAN Network Applications
University of Malaga Spain 6G-SANDBOX		O-RAN; NSSF Network Application
CWC research unit at Oulu 6G-SANDBOX		None
KUL, Leuven, Belgium, 6G-BRICKS		O-RAN
Sophia Tech Open5GLab, France 6G-BRICKS	Open Calls; Use cases: Metaverse as an Enabler for a Modern Workplace; Holoconferencing: Telepresence in a Broadcasting environment; Multiuser Team Building Activities with Advanced Full Volumetric Capture and in-cloud Media Processing; Autonomous robots in Industry 4.0; AR inspection for INdustry 4.0 digital twin on site	O-RAN NWDAF NSSF Network Application
5Gtonic, Madrid, Spain, 6G-XR	Open calls; MST: Magos Surgical Training	CAPIF;NSSF; Network Application
5G-Barcelona, Spain 6G-XR	Open calls ExCalibAR: User-friendly intrinsic and extrinsic calibration for multi-light-field cameras for AR/VR; METAPHOR: Volumetric Capture and Transmission in Broadcast Environments; OpenCAMARA: Open source solution to integrate CAMARA QoD API to 5G stack; REQUIEM: Research on QUIC client mobility	O-RAN NSSF Network Application
VTT 5GTN Technical Research centre, Finland, 6G-XR	Open calls: BANQ: Bringing Automated Network QoS Monitoring Capabilities for Research Infrastructures	O-RAN; NSSF Network Application
OULU 5G Test Network (5GTN), University of Oulu Finland 6G-XR	Open calls: Enabling end-to-end O-RAN slicing in 6G-XR; BANQ: Bringing Automated Network QoS Monitoring Capabilities for Research Infrastructures; FALADIN: Fab Lab digital twin environment	O-RAN NSSF ZSM; Network Application
5G- Industry Campus Europe Trial Site 5G-ICE, TARGET-X	Open calls; +Use Cases: Verticals: Manufacturing & robotics; Construction; Energy: 5G for energy awareness, 5G for monitoring, and increasing sustainability	None
Idiada Automotive (IDAID) Spain, TARGET-X	Open calls + Use cases: Automotive verticals: Cooperative perception for Connected Automated Vehicles (CAVs); Digital Road Twin; Predictive Quality of Service	None
Orange Romania, IMEC Antwerp, Belgium TrialsNet	Open calls; +Use cases: Smart crowd monitoring; Smart traffic management	SEAL/CAPIF; O-RAN; NSSF; Advanced Slicing; ZSM; Network Application
Turin site, Italy TrialsNet	Open calls; + Use cases: Remote Proctoring; Smart Ambulance	NSSF; Advanced Slicing; ZSM; Network Application
5Tonic Madrid, Spain TrialsNet	Open Calls; + Use cases: Smart crowd monitoring; Mass causality incident and emergency resource in populated areas; Immersive fan management	CAPIF; NSSF; Advanced Slicing; ZSM; Network Application
Greece, site TrialsNet	Open calls; + Use cases: Proactive public infrastructure asset management; autonomous parking, unloading of aircraft; Mass casualty incident and emergency rescue populated areas Service robots for enhanced passenger’s experience; XR museum experience	CAPIF; NWDAF; NSSF; Advanced Slicing; ZSM; Network Application
Patras5G/PNET, Greece FIDAL	Open Calls + Use cases: Digital Twin for first responders; Advanced sports area media services; XR-assisted services for public safety	CAPIF; O-RAN; NWDAF; NSSF; Network Exposure; ZSM; Network Application
UMA VICTORIA Malaga Spain, FIDAL	Open calls + Use cases: Internet of Senses/Haptic Sensing; City security event/incident	O-RAN; NSSF; ZSM; Network Application
Telnor LST Facility Norway FIDAL	Open calls +Use cases: VR Networked music performance; Smart village engagement services	CAPIF; NSSF; Advanced slicing; ZSM; Network Application
EURECOM SophiaTech Open5GLab France IMAGINE-B5G	Open calls + Use cases: PPDR: Firefighting and forest surveillance	CAPIF; NSSF/NSMF; NEF with CAMRA; O-RAN; Advanced slicing; ZSM; Network Application
Telnor, Nokia-Finland, Norway IMAGINE-B5G	Open calls; +Use cases: PPDR: VR/AR-enabled dispersed command post; Media: Robust and flexible remote production; Industry 4.0: Industrial Infrastructure Automation Education: Immersive remote education; Agriculture & Forestry: Forestry connectivity and monitoring; eHealth: Remote care with immersive media facilities	CAPIF; O-RAN; NSSF; NEF with CAMRA; Advanced slicing; ZSM; Network Application
Altice Labs, Portugal IMAGINE-B5G	Open calls +Use cases: PPDR: IoT Platform for crisis management; T&L: Improved localization mechanisms for T&L; eHealth: Enhanced care facilities	CAPIF; NWDAF; NSSF; NEF with CAMARA; Advanced slicing; ZSM; Network Application
Telefonica, Nokia, Spain IMAGINE-B5G	Open calls + Use cases: PPDR: Critical surveillance and inspection at maritime ports and Multi-functional remotely operated boat; Media: Holographic communication; T&L: Telepresence-aided maintenance; Education: Immersive remote education- Agriculture & Forestry: Smart agriculture in rural areas	CAPIF; NSSF/NSMF; NEF with CAMARA; Advanced slicing; ZSM; Network Application

It is important to highlight that 70% **Stream C** trial facilities support O-RAN (Table III). Additionally, 20% of the facilities support CAPIF, which promotes the openness and programmability of B5G. In combination with O-RAN, CAPIF enables greater customization of RAN. Vertical service providers can tailor RAN functionalities to specific use cases and industry requirements. For example, vertical services can dynamically steer the beamforming of the Next-Generation Node B (gNodeB) towards teleoperated vehicles (Fig. 2).

On the other hand, **Stream D** projects support all B5G capabilities, except the 3GPP EDGEAPP framework (Table III). However, 8% of them support the 3GPP SEAL framework, and 61% support the CAPIF framework. Thus, even in the absence of the EDGEAPP framework, vertical service providers can still enhance their services using the SEAL framework. However, these services will not be deployed at the edge as envisioned by 3GPP. Specifically, these services will miss some enhancements provided by the EDGEAPP framework, such as low latency and real-time processing. Nevertheless, with the maturity of these frameworks in standards we expect higher adoption in trial sites.

Compared to Stream C, 38% of Stream D projects provide advanced network slice orchestration leveraging the NSMF. All these selected B5G technologies combined (i.e., CAPIF, SEAL, NWDAF, NSSF/NSMF, network exposure capabilities) make these facilities relevant candidates for testing and validating vertical services.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

A. Trial site Facilities

1) **Trial facility trustworthiness:** To fully exploit the advancements of 5G and 6G networks, it is imperative for vertical industries to have access to network deployments that are a solid representation of current and future commercial deployments. This fidelity is essential as it allows vertical industries to develop and test their services with confidence, ensuring that the transition from a trial facility environment to a live network is seamless and successful. Thus, to enhance trustworthiness, trial facilities should:

- **Align with Real-World Network Conditions:** Incorporate real-time data and feedback from operational networks to simulate current network performance accurately. Enable testing under a variety of conditions, including peak loads and stress scenarios that services may encounter in live networks.
- **Validate Against Industry Benchmarks:** Regularly benchmark testbed performance against industry standards and real-world network deployments to ensure relevance and reliability.
- **Facilitate Transparency:** Provide clear documentation and open channels of communication regarding the capabilities and limitations of the trial facility infrastructure.
- **Ensure Realistic placement of trial facilities:** The trial facilities should be geographically placed in locations to ensure that vertical services are validated in similar environments where they will eventually be deployed. For example, vertical services tailored to maritime use cases should be validated in real-life port environments [1].

By adhering to the above-mentioned principles, trial facilities can serve as a reliable proxy for the actual network environment, thus empowering vertical industries to innovate and validate their services with the assurance that they will perform as expected (or close to it) when deployed in the real world.

2) **Opportunities for upgrading current trial facilities:** With the ICT-41 program finishing, Stream D is further building on top of these trial facilities. In that process it is important to include as many as possible B5G technologies discussed in this article. This becomes even more pressing with initiatives like SNS JU phases 2 (focused on 6G detailed design) and 3 (focused on pre-commercial 6G systems) spanning from 2025 until 2031.

3) **Integration of EdgeApps with network:** The ICT-41 trial facilities primarily focus on the advanced 5G capabilities brought by Network Applications, i.e., EdgeApps. These applications have the potential to abstract underlying network complexities. The next step with EdgeApps is to tighten the integration with the network itself and to use NWDAF to improve the performance, by retrieving important network metrics (e.g., latency, bandwidth, throughput, signal strength, among others).

4) **Need for advanced network slicing and orchestration:** The SNS JU phase 1 trial facilities, while also supporting Network Applications, increasingly prioritize advanced network slicing and orchestration capabilities. They are important because of the increased network complexity that is becoming even present in 6G. Such complexity requires automated and intelligent management of resources, through the increased use of AI to make decision-making smarter.

5) **Importance of network programmability through APIs:** As networks adopt programmable exposure technologies like APIs (e.g., CAMARA by GSMA, CAPIF by 3GPP), trial facilities should incorporate these capabilities. The limited support of network exposure prevents researchers and vertical industries from validating the integration of new technologies. This limitation restricts the exploration of more advanced network slicing and orchestration solutions that leverage network exposure capabilities to make more intelligent and proactive decisions about service and slice reconfiguration, which ultimately impacts service performance.

6) **Importance of collaborative trial facilities for testing and validating vertical services:** Our analysis shows that there is a significant amount of funding involved in creating numerous trial facilities provided and operated by governments, academia, standardization bodies, MNOs around the world. This highlights the importance of these initiatives. The trial facilities should incentivize SMEs and startups, allowing them to effectively test and validate their services before deployment in commercial networks. This approach offers several benefits:

- Vertical service providers are more likely to engage with such trial sites, knowing they are supported by telecom operators and governments. This addresses the current issue of many trial facilities shutting down after project funding ends, forcing service providers to seek new opportunities. Strategically placed and sustainable trial facilities should be made operational in the decades to come.
- Access to state-of-the-art network technologies and the expertise that exists in such consortia benefits vertical service providers, as collaboration among stakeholders facilitates the use of the latest systems with direct industry and research community support. This is especially relevant as there exists a gap, particularly among SME, in understanding how B5G technologies can enhance their day-to-day operations, as this is not their primary expertise.
- Collaboration between academics from different universities and industry research teams becomes more efficient,

enabling the testing and validation of new research ideas with the feedback of domain expertise.

- Centralized hubs, involving multiple telecommunication vendors and O-RAN vendors, can efficiently test cross-domain scenarios, enhancing testing comprehensiveness even in multi-MNO cross-border setups.

B. B5G Vertical Services

When trial facilities (Tables II and III) incorporate the Baseline 5G and B5G technologies identified in this article, vertical services can be enhanced through Network Applications/EdgeApps by allowing them to:

- **Dynamically re-program the network:** By using network exposure capabilities such as APIs (SEAL/CAPIF and CAMARA), the vertical service can in real-time trigger dynamic re-programming of the underlying slice to adapt it to evolving conditions without potentially violating SLA agreements.
- **Enhance slice orchestration:** Vertical services can potentially improve the orchestration of slices, by interacting via APIs with the NSSF and NSMF. This can enrich the understanding of NSSF and NSMF about real-time network and compute performance at the application level, making them derive more sophisticated decisions.
- **Explore O-RAN solutions:** O-RAN enables vertical services to re-program the radio as well, enabling functionalities such as beam steering towards a dedicated UE. For example, when an autonomous ship enters a port area requiring teleoperation, the beam can be steered to track the ship, optimizing the teleoperation experience for the remote captain. Additionally, O-RAN fosters more competitiveness among MNOs, potentially leading to better service offerings and innovations in the telecommunication sector.
- **Optimize resource consumption:** Following the SEAL and EdgeApp philosophy, vertical services can be designed as resource-aware to apply QoS or QoE enhancements only when necessary, thereby optimizing network resource management and minimizing resource consumption.
- **Emulate real-life conditions:** Vertical services require trial facilities that can accurately emulate real-world conditions, including network variability, device heterogeneity, and user behavior patterns. This ensures that vertical applications are tested against scenarios that closely mimic their operational environment.

C. Scalability and Cost Considerations

As 6G trial facilities and networks, in general, continue to evolve, scalability and cost efficiency become important for widespread deployment across various verticals. The B5G capabilities discussed in this article collectively contribute to the scalability of 6G networks by simplifying the network architecture toward vertical industries by offering them simplified interfaces that they can leverage to test and experience innovative technologies.

1) **System Complexity and Scalability:** 6G networks are expected to become simpler and more efficient by integrating advanced B5G capabilities, as outlined in this article, such as the 3GPP vertical service frameworks (e.g., SEAL, CAPIF, and EDGEAPP), Network Applications, ZSM, Network Exposure capabilities. These technologies abstract network complexity

from verticals, enabling them to create new services tailored to enhance their day-to-day operations.

To fully realize this simplification and scalability, 6G networks will leverage several key innovations that optimize performance, enhance adaptability, and ensure seamless service delivery. These advancements include AI-driven network slicing for dynamic resource management, distributed edge architectures for scalable computing, and IBN for automated scaling. The following highlights how each of these components contributes to the overarching goal of efficient and scalable 6G systems:

- **AI-Driven Network Slicing & Adaptive Resource Management:** Unlike traditional static network slicing, AI-enhanced NSMF/NSSF functions will enable dynamic scaling of network slices based on demand fluctuations [47–49]. Real-time analytics from NWDAF, powered by AI/ML, provide predictive insights into network performance, user behavior, and resource utilization. While NWDAF itself does not make decisions, its analytics help AI-driven systems in other NFs to perform smarter decisions about bandwidth allocation and resource optimization to keep the network running smoothly. For example, in a 6G environment, an AI-based NF can adjust bandwidth for remote-controlled vessels based on real-time demand using information from the NWDAF. If a ship needs to send more control commands and high-definition video due to complex navigation in a busy port, AI can use NWDAF analytics and past traffic patterns to predict this increase and adjust resources accordingly.
- **Distributed and Hierarchical Architectures for Scaling Edge Computing:** With increasing reliance on edge computing, hierarchical edge-cloud models will be necessary to scale applications efficiently [48]. Multi-tier edge architectures will distribute processing loads across micro-edge nodes, regional data centers, and centralized cloud infrastructure, allowing verticals to run compute-intensive applications at scale while maintaining ultra-low latency.
- **IBN for Automated Scaling:** Future 6G networks will leverage IBN over standardized APIs to automatically adjust network configurations based on service-level intents [17]. This ensures that resources are provisioned dynamically for large-scale applications like autonomous vehicles, smart cities, and IIoT without requiring manual intervention.

2) **Cost Reduction through Infrastructure Sharing and Virtualization:** To address the high costs associated with deploying and maintaining 6G infrastructure, O-RAN presents a solution by promoting infrastructure sharing. O-RAN enables MNOs to mix and match hardware and software from various vendors, reducing vendor lock-in and fostering competition. This open approach can significantly lower costs, making 6G adoption more accessible for a range of verticals [50].

Additionally, 6G needs to inherit best practices from 5G in terms of virtualization and overall network softwareization to support further cost reduction by enabling network functions to run on shared, flexible cloud infrastructure. For instance, through Virtual Network Function (VNF), 6G networks can efficiently manage resources, adapt to real-time needs, and minimize the need for costly physical infrastructure upgrades.

Several key enablers will contribute to ensuring 6G networks remain economically viable while scaling globally. These include adopting Network-as-a-service (NaaS) models for dynamic infrastructure sharing, leveraging O-RAN and Software-

Defined Networking (SDN) for efficient resource pooling, and implementing multi-cloud integration frameworks for seamless scalability. The following highlights how these approaches will support cost-efficient scaling and sustainable 6G deployment:

- *NaaS Models for Cost-Efficient Scaling:* NaaS frameworks will allow multiple vertical industries to share network infrastructure, compute power, and spectrum resources dynamically, reducing Capital Expenditure (CAPEX) and Operational Expenditure (OPEX) [51]. Cloud-native service mesh architectures will enable on-demand instantiation of 6G functions across multiple domains.
- *O-RAN and SDN for Resource Pooling:* The disaggregation of RAN and Core via SDN-driven Network Function Virtualization (NFV) will enable cost-efficient scaling by allowing operators to instantiate lightweight, cloud-based network functions when required, rather than deploying expensive dedicated hardware [52].
- *Multi-Cloud Integration for Global Scalability:* Multi-cloud and hybrid-cloud orchestration frameworks will be crucial for large-scale 6G deployments, enabling operators to seamlessly scale network services across public, private, and edge cloud environments. This will allow enterprises to balance cost efficiency and performance needs.

3) *Sustainability and Energy Efficiency:* Scalability and cost-effectiveness in 6G are closely linked to sustainability. Technologies like intelligent resource allocation and the use of AI for predictive maintenance can help optimize energy use, leading to lower operational costs. These enhancements align with the growing need for environmentally friendly networks, as industries seek to reduce both expenses and carbon footprint.

To achieve these sustainability goals, 6G networks will incorporate innovative approaches that balance performance with energy efficiency. From AI-powered workload distribution to next-generation green RAN solutions and federated learning for large-scale AI optimization, the following key strategies will be essential for building energy-conscious 6G ecosystems:

- *AI-Powered Energy Optimization for Dynamic Workload Distribution:* AI-driven energy-aware algorithms can dynamically allocate workloads across network nodes based on real-time energy availability and traffic demand, ensuring optimal power efficiency in large-scale 6G deployments [53].
- *Green RAN and Zero-Touch Energy-Aware Management:* Next-generation green RAN solutions [16] will incorporate dynamic power-saving features, such as AI-powered beamforming, adaptive sleep modes for base stations, and energy-efficient fronthaul solutions to reduce carbon footprint while maintaining service reliability.
- *Federated Learning for Efficient Model Training at Scale:* To handle AI-driven network optimization at scale, federated learning techniques will be adopted, allowing distributed AI models to be trained across multiple edge nodes without requiring centralized data aggregation [54]. This enhances both scalability and data privacy.

By incorporating the aforementioned B5G technologies, 6G networks will be able to scale efficiently across diverse deployment scenarios while reducing costs and improving energy efficiency.

4) *Interoperability Challenges in Multi-Vendor 6G Networks:* As 6G networks evolve towards more open, disaggregated, and software-driven architectures, interoperability between different vendors and platforms becomes a key challenge. Unlike previous generations, where end-to-end solu-

tions were provided by a single vendor, 6G is expected to support multi-vendor deployments integrating O-RAN, cloud-native network functions, and AI-driven orchestration. However, ensuring seamless interoperability across heterogeneous network components, including RAN, Core, and Edge, remains complex due to variations in protocol implementations, API exposure, and orchestration frameworks. Furthermore, the transition to software-defined and virtualized infrastructures amplifies interoperability concerns, particularly in managing network slicing, dynamic resource allocation, and multi-cloud deployments. Addressing these challenges requires a combination of standardization efforts, testing frameworks, and cross-domain orchestration mechanisms, which we discuss in detail below:

- 1) *Complexity of Multi-Vendor Integration:* In traditional networks, hardware and software are tightly coupled, making interoperability difficult. With O-RAN and SDN, operators can mix and match components, but this introduces challenges in standardizing APIs, protocols, and orchestration layers.
- 2) *Challenges in RAN and Core Interoperability:*
 - O-RAN decouples radio hardware from software, but interoperability issues arise due to varying implementations of the O-RAN stack across vendors.
 - 3GPP and O-RAN Alliance define standards, but practical challenges remain in ensuring seamless interworking of network functions (e.g., different RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC) implementations may have vendor-specific optimizations).
- 3) *Network Exposure and API Standardization:*
 - While network exposure frameworks (CAPIF, SEAL, and CAMARA) enable cross-vendor compatibility, ensuring uniform API implementation across vendors is challenging.
 - The lack of unified authentication and security protocols for exposed network functions hinders seamless interconnection between different platforms.
- 4) *Orchestration and Automation Across Heterogeneous Environments*
 - The rise of AI-driven automation (e.g., ZSM) requires interoperability across different AI models, which may not be designed to interact across vendor ecosystems.
 - Multi-cloud orchestration faces challenges as each vendor implements different virtualization frameworks (e.g., Kubernetes variations, OpenStack vs. Amazon Web Services (AWS) solutions).
- 5) *Standardization Efforts to Overcome Interoperability Challenges*
 - 3GPP, GSMA OGI, and O-RAN Alliance are working towards harmonizing protocols.
 - Interoperability certification programs (e.g., O-RAN PlugFests) should be integrated into trial facilities to validate real-world interoperability before commercial rollout.

D. Regulatory and Market Readiness Considerations

While 6G is still in the research and early standardization phase, with commercial deployment expected around 2030, ensuring regulatory compliance and assessing market readiness will be crucial for its successful deployment. While innovations in O-RAN, AI-driven automation, and network exposure

frameworks accelerate technological advancements, regulatory challenges and economic constraints can significantly influence the pace and scale of adoption.

1) *Regulatory Considerations:*

- *Spectrum Allocation and Policy Harmonization:* Regulatory bodies such as the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) play a central role in defining spectrum policies for 6G, while organizations like 3GPP and GSMA contribute to technical standards and industry advocacy. The availability of mmWave, sub-THz, and AI-optimized dynamic spectrum allocation is crucial for enabling ultra-high-speed connectivity. However, differences in regional spectrum policies can hinder cross-border trials and deployments.
- *Data Privacy, AI Governance, and Cybersecurity Compliance:* Given that 6G networks are expected to rely heavily on AI-driven automation, IBN, and real-time analytics, ensuring compliance with regulations, such as General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (Europe), California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA) United States of America (U.S.), and AI Act frameworks is essential. Additionally, concerns regarding data sovereignty and network exposure security require standardized policies to protect sensitive vertical services.
- *Standardization and Vendor Interoperability:* Initiatives such as the O-RAN Alliance and 3GPP Rel-18+ standards aim to ensure multi-vendor compatibility, while the GSMA OGI focuses on API-based interoperability across telecom networks. However, the lack of universally enforced certification mechanisms may delay interoperability across different regions. Establishing common testing frameworks and regulatory-driven certification programs will be necessary to ensure seamless integration across diverse 6G infrastructure providers.

2) *Market Readiness for 6G Deployments:*

- *Public-Private Partnerships for Accelerated Adoption:* 6G deployment requires significant investment from telecom operators, infrastructure providers, and governmental bodies. Funding programs such as the European SNS JU and national-level 6G strategies (e.g., Japan's Beyond 5G Promotion Strategy, U.S. CHIPS and Science Act) provide financial incentives to trial sites, startups, and research institutions to bridge the gap between prototype and real-world deployment.
- *Challenges in Commercialization and Business Model Evolution:* Unlike previous generations, 6G networks will not be purely operator-driven. Instead, hyperscalers, private enterprises, and industry consortia will play a more significant role in network ownership and monetization. New business models, such as NaaS, AI-optimized spectrum leasing, and decentralized 6G marketplaces, will need to be tested within trial sites to determine their feasibility and Return On Investment (ROI).

Generally, the large-scale deployment of 6G will depend on how well the industry addresses regulatory misalignment, adoption barriers, and trial site sustainability. Key efforts should focus on developing policy-driven interoperability frameworks, improving cross-border compliance, and refining commercialization strategies across industries. Tackling these challenges early will help ensure 6G is not just a technical upgrade but a viable, scalable solution with real economic impact.

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VII. BIOGRAPHY SECTION

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